

Optimization of Treatment of Intrahepatic Cholestasis of Pregnancy

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Abstract: Cholestasis of pregnancy is a variant of dermatosis of pregnancy caused by idiopathic intrahepatic bile stasis. It manifests itself as itching of the skin, yellowing of the skin, dyspeptic symptoms, light stools, darkening of urine. Diagnosed on the basis of data on the level of bile acids, bilirubin, liver enzymes, hemostasis factors, confirmed by the results of ultrasound examination of the liver. Ursodeoxycholic acid, hepatoprotectors, cholagogues, antihistamines, vitamin-mineral complexes, enterosorbents and detoxification therapy are used for treatment.

Keywords: Causes, Pathogenesis, Classification, Symptoms of cholestasis during pregnancy, Diagnosis, Differential diagnosis.

Introduction

The prevalence of cholestasis during pregnancy (recurrent cholestatic jaundice, pregnancy pruritus) is 0.1% to 2%. The disease is often found in Bolivia, Chile, Scandinavia, China and the northern regions of Russia. Pathology often has a family character. Women who take estrogen-progestogen oral contraceptives and antibiotics before pregnancy are more likely to develop cholestasis of pregnancy. The risk group also includes patients with intolerance to macrolides, erythromycins, gastrointestinal tract pathology and endocrine diseases. During repeated pregnancies, the risk of recurrence of obstetric jaundice reaches 60-80%.

The Role of Compensatory Competence

The etiology of pregnancy pruritus has not yet been clearly defined. Since the disease is associated with pregnancy and often manifests itself in several women of the same family, hormonal changes in susceptible patients play a leading role in its development. Specialists in the field of obstetrics consider the main conditions for the occurrence of cholestasis during pregnancy:

Estrogen concentration increase. By the end of pregnancy, the level of estrogen hormones increases more than 1000 times. By binding to hepatocyte receptors, estrogens increase cholesterol synthesis and thus change the composition of bile. Under their influence, pregnant women also experience an imbalance of bile acids: the concentration of deoxycholic and chenodeoxycholic acids decreases and the amount of cholic acid increases. Due to a decrease in the activity of liver transport proteins, the level of bile acids in the bile decreases and, accordingly, their blood flow increases. Changes are more pronounced in high hyperestrogenism, which is characteristic of multiple pregnancies.

Increased sensitivity to estrogen. Changes in the bile colloid balance occur in all pregnant women, but only some of them develop clinically clear cholestasis with skin itching. Perhaps this is due to genetic abnormalities that change the sensitivity of liver cells and bile ducts to estrogen hormones or affect the activity of enzyme systems that ensure the synthesis and transport of bile acids.

Confirmation of the hereditary nature of cholestasis of pregnancy is significantly more frequent detection of HLA-A31, HLA-w16, HLA-B8 tissue antigens in pregnant women with obstetric jaundice and their relatives.

An additional factor contributing to the violation of bile flow and the increase in the amount of bile acids in the blood plasma is the effect of progesterone. Progestins have a relaxing effect on smooth muscle fibers, which leads to deterioration of the movement of the gallbladder and bile ducts, increases intrahepatic stagnation of bile. In addition, by slowing down the intestinal movement, the reabsorption of bile acids is disturbed and their balance worsens.

Pathogenesis

The mechanism of cholestasis in pregnant women is associated with the irritating effect of bile acids on skin receptors, and their concentration in the blood increases during intrahepatic stagnation of bile. The leading pathophysiological component of hepatocellular cholestasis is a decrease in fluidity of the basolateral and somewhat less often canalicular membrane. The permeability of the cell membrane is disturbed due to the congenital deficiency of transporter proteins and the deficiency of hepatobiliary transport due to the increase in cholesterol concentration under the influence of estrogens.

These factors reduce the activity of S-adenosylmethylnthetase and inhibit the synthesis of S-adenomethionine. As a result, the course of biochemical processes in hepatocytes becomes more unstable, hepatocyte membranes lose phospholipids, the activity of Na-K-ATPase and other transport proteins decreases, the reserves of the main detoxifying substances (glutathione, taurine, other thiols and sulfates) decrease.) decreases, which causes cell cytolysis with additional entry of toxic components into the blood

Classification

When systematizing the forms of intrahepatic cholestasis of pregnancy, experts in the field of gastroenterology and hepatology take into account changes in biochemical indicators and the severity of the disease. The most favorable prognosis is the partial bilirubin variant of the disorder, mainly the synthesis and secretion of bilirubin is impaired, while the metabolism of the remaining components of bile is preserved. Cholestasis in pregnant women, which poses the greatest danger to women and children, is partly in the form of choleacid, in the process of normal transport of other components, the absorption or secretion of bile acids is disturbed. To choose a tactic for an accompanying pregnancy, the severity of the disease should be taken into account:

Light level . Mild itching of the skin. The activity of transaminases increases 2-3 times, the amount of alkaline phosphatase and gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase increases. There are no other clinical or laboratory signs of the disease. The risk of obstetric complications is minimal, the duration of pregnancy can be extended.

Average level . Severe itching of the skin. ALT and AST activity increases 3-6 times, cholesterol, alkaline phosphatase and GGTP concentrations increase, hemostasis indicators are disturbed. Ultrasound can detect biliary sludge. The most common form of the disease with possible fetoplacental insufficiency and fetal development delay.

Heavy degree . In addition to itching of the skin and a significant increase in enzyme activity, increased laboratory signs of coagulopathy and clinical signs of gastroenterological diseases were noted. Due to the high probability of a complicated course and even the death of the fetus, it is recommended to terminate the pregnancy early.

Symptoms of cholestasis during pregnancy

Usually the disease occurs at 36-40 weeks of pregnancy, less often at the end of the 2nd trimester. The disorder first appears as skin symptoms. A pregnant woman experiences itching of varying

intensity, from minor to painful. Itching is localized primarily in the area of the palms and feet, then spreads to the back, abdomen and other parts of the body and becomes general. Areas of excoriation (scratching) complicated by a secondary purulent process can be identified on the skin.

An inconsistent sign of cholestasis is jaundice, which appears 1-2 weeks after the onset of itching, accompanied by darkening of urine and lightness of feces. In severe cases, there are complaints of nausea, itching, palpitations, loss of appetite, heaviness in the epigastrium, dull pain in the right hypochondrium, and rarely vomiting. A pregnant woman becomes lethargic, apathetic and inhibited. 7-15 days after birth, the disease passes by itself.

Cholestasis in pregnant women usually does not serve as a contraindication to continue pregnancy, but in moderate and severe cases it has a negative effect on it. With prolonged cholemia, energy metabolism is sharply disturbed, hypoxia increases, and cytotoxic effects occur, which leads to fetoplacental insufficiency, fetal development delay, and an increase in perinatal mortality up to 4.7%. Antenatal fetal death with repeated cholestasis is observed 4 times more often than in normal pregnancy. Up to 35% of births lead to the birth of a premature baby with signs of hypoxia.

Premature birth of pregnant women with cholestatic liver jaundice is observed in 12-44% of cases, respiratory distress syndrome is often diagnosed, and meconium is detected in amniotic fluid. Hemostasis disorders develop due to insufficient absorption of vitamin K. As a result, the risk of obstetric coagulopathic bleeding and disseminated intravascular coagulation increases.

Postpartum increases the likelihood of endometritis. Pregnancy itching is repeated during the next pregnancy when taking oral contraceptives. In the long term, such patients often suffer from cholelithiasis, cholecystitis, non-alcoholic forms of hepatitis, liver cirrhosis and chronic pancreatitis.

Diagnosics

Since itching and yellowing of the skin is detected not only in pregnant women with cholestasis, but also in a number of skin, infectious and somatic diseases, the task of the diagnostic search is to exclude symptoms characteristic of other diseases. during pregnancy. The recommended examination plan for patients with suspected cholestasis during pregnancy includes the following laboratory and instrumental methods:

Determination of bile acid level. The study is considered screening and allows to detect cholestasis in pregnant women at the preclinical stage. The amount of cholic acid increased and the level of chenodeoxycholic acid decreased against the background of a general increase in the concentration of bile acids in the blood serum.

Liver tests. Symptoms of intrahepatic cholestasis are a moderate increase in the content of direct bilirubin, α - and β -globulins, triglycerides and β -lipoproteins. Cholesterol is clearly elevated. Albumin level is slightly reduced. An increase in the activity of alkaline phosphatase, GGGT, ALT, AST and 5'-nucleotidase is observed.

Hemostasiogram . The moderate and severe course of the disease is characterized by changes in the hemostatic system with an increase in aPTT and prothrombin time.

Ultrasound examination of the liver and biliary tract. The liver of a pregnant woman has normal dimensions and a homogeneous ecostructure. There may be a change in the acoustic density of the liver tissue and the appearance of biliary sludge. The gallbladder often enlarges, the intrahepatic bile ducts expand, and the echogenicity of their walls increases.

Differential diagnosis.

Gestational cholestasis differs from other dermatoses of pregnant women, acute fatty hepatitis during pregnancy, HELLP syndrome, late gestosis, viral hepatitis, cholelithiasis, drug-induced cholestatic jaundice, liver cancer, hereditary liver pathology (hemochromatosis, Kononov-V syndrome).) and other diseases. Infectious mononucleosis and cytomegalovirus infection are

excluded. According to the indications, the patient is consulted by a dermatologist, an infectious disease specialist, a gastroenterologist, a hepatologist, a toxicologist and an oncologist.

Treatment of cholestasis during pregnancy

Drug therapy

When accompanying women with gestational jaundice, it is preferable to treat pregnancy with careful monitoring of laboratory parameters and fetal status. The main therapeutic goal is to eliminate the symptoms of bile stagnation, which have a negative effect on the child's body. The drug treatment scheme depends on the severity of cholestasis of pregnancy and usually includes the use of the following drugs:

Ursodeoxycholic acid. The drug affects the main links of pathogenesis and is the main one in the treatment of the disorder. Due to its high hydrophilicity, it effectively protects the biliary tract from the effects of hydrophobic bile acids and stimulates the excretion of hepatotoxic components of bile. Safe for the fetus.

Hepatoprotectors and cholagogues. Agents affecting the state of liver cells and bile secretion reduce the risk of damage to hepatocytes, improve their activity and reduce congestion in the bile system.

In the case of general itching, a rapid increase in laboratory parameters, especially high cholemia, enterosorbents and detoxification therapy (hemoadsorption, plasmapheresis) are used to remove substances from the body that cause itching sensations. The use of antioxidants (ascorbic acid, vitamin E) is effective for all forms of the disease. Antihistamines can be prescribed to relieve itching. The use of systemic glucocorticosteroids is limited due to possible toxic effects on the fetus.

Diet

Drug therapy for cholestasis is combined with dietary correction. It is recommended to supplement the diet of a pregnant woman with protein products (chicken, beef, veal), dietary fiber, fat-soluble vitamins, folic and linoleic acids, and limit the consumption of fatty, spicy and fried foods. .

Delivery

With mild and moderate severity of the disease, pregnancy ends with natural birth at a physiological time. If cholestasis occurs with severe jaundice, cholemia approaches 40 mmol / l, if there is a threat to the life of the fetus, early delivery is carried out at 36 weeks or more. Cesarean section is performed when fetal asphyxia threatens or begins, or when other obstetric symptoms are detected.

Conclusion

Mild to moderate cholestasis of pregnancy may result in a positive pregnancy outcome. In severe cases, the prognosis worsens, especially if the disorder manifests itself in the second trimester. Early registration in the antenatal clinic, regular examinations by an obstetrician-gynecologist, and regular consultations are recommended for patients suffering from cholestatic jaundice during a previous pregnancy, who have a hereditary family history, or who will give birth to multiple fetuses. screening blood test for gastroenterology and bile acids.

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